

A Crossover Design on Effectiveness & Comparison of 3 Different Innovative Teaching Method in Case Based Learning for First Year MBBS on Biochemistry at CIMS, Chikkamagaluru

Manasa D.R¹, Shabnam S², Ramkrishna B.Yadgude³, Avinash S.S⁴, Srinivas Deshpande⁵, Drisya Kaladharan⁶, Hitaish Kumar R.N⁷

^{1,2}Assistant Professor, Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru

³Medical Officer, PHC Belgundi, Belgavi

⁴Associate Professor, Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru

⁵Professor & HOD, Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru

^{6,7}Tutor, Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 26-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Avinash S.S

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Objective: Fishbowlw Case Based Learning (CBL), forms a bridging gap between theory & and practice, to achieve reasoning skills and competence we introduced 3 different teaching techniques Fish Bowl (FB), Jigsaw (JS), and Flipped Classroom (FCR) among MBBS students.

Methodology: A crossover design study was done among first-year MBBS students for a period of 6 weeks at CIMS, Chikkamagaluru. A total of 150 students were divided into 3 groups (50 in each group) and underwent 3 rounds so that each group was exposed to all 3 techniques. Assessment was done by conducting pretest and post-test MCQs. Feedback was taken from both students and facilitators.

Results: The difference in the means of analysis between two-time points in the same group was tested by paired t-test. Significant improvement in performance pre v/s posttest. Difference of means analyzed by ANOVA & F testing. 1st & 2nd round showed FCR had higher mean (7±1.7, 7.8±1.2) compared to JS (6.3±2.1, 7.4±1.6) and FB (6.6±2, 7.5±1.7) whereas 3rd round showed FB & FCR were had higher mean (6.2±1.9, 6.2±1.7) which was statistically significant at (p<0.001) compared to jigsaw (6.1±2).

Conclusion: Our study showed there is a positive reinforcement & and improvement in the student's performance among FCR & FB teaching techniques compared to the JS method.

Keywords: Cased Based Learning, Fishbowl, Jigsaw, Flipped Classroom, Clinical Biochemistry.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Clinical biochemistry is a foundational subject that gives a biochemical basis and diagnostic approach to most diseases [1,2]. Hence Case-based learning closes the loopholes between theory and practice by providing veritable case scenarios to the students under the aegis of inquisitive-based learning which is composed of 5 E elements i.e., Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, and Evaluate [3].

Under Bloom's revised taxonomy, teacher-centered learning makes students engross only a one-horse cart [4]. On the other hand, there is a gap between knowledge concerning & and knowledge retention in teaching Biochemistry.

A famous educationalist John Holt said "Learning is not the product of teaching. Learning is the product of the activity of learners" [5], thus we introduced 3 different innovative teaching techniques for Case-based learning such as Fishbowl (FB),

Jigsaw (JS), and Flipped Classroom (FCR) where all 3 were student's-centered approaches.

The fishbowl (FB) method ameliorates the communication skills of students for a labyrinthine discussion and involves the active participation of students creating a more efficient, productive, and engaging classroom environment [6,7,8]. Whereas Jigsaw (JS) is cooperative learning in which students work in small groups, each student feels validated [9], and primarily used for the acquisition [10] and presentation of new material [11]. In the case of the flipped classroom (FCR), it is a blended learning where students learn foundational material from outside of the classroom via online, annotated PPTs or any other resources thereby enhancing critical thinking and reasoning skills to achieve competence [12].

Methodology

A crossover study design was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry at the Chikkamagluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagluru, Karnataka for a period of 6 weeks. The study commenced after getting ethical clearance from the Institution and informed consent from students. Conducted 3 rounds so that all students were exposed to all 3 techniques i.e. Fishbowl Method, Jigsaw Method & Flipped Classroom (FCR). A total of 150 students were divided into 3 groups. Each group consisted of 50 students each.

First Round Nearly 138 students were present on that day. Cases were Alcoholic liver disease, Mul-

tle Myeloma, Acute inflammation due to rheumatoid arthritis, and Nephrotic Syndrome.

Second Round: Nearly 135 students were present. Cases were Beta-thalassemia major, Beta-thalassemia minor, Sickle Cell Anemia, and Homozygous Sickle Cell Anemia.

Third Round: Nearly 135 students were present. Cases were Carbon monoxide poisoning, Acquired methemoglobinemia, and congenital methemoglobinemia.

For each technique, facilitators were assigned to this study.

Table 1:

Group	First Round	Second Round	Third Round
I Group (1-50)	Jigsaw	Fish Bowl	Flipped Classroom
II Group (51-100)	Flipped Classroom	Jigsaw	Fish Bowl
III Group (101-150)	Fish Bowl	Flipped Classroom	Jigsaw

Fish Bowl Methodology

Figure 1: The Fishbowl

Step 1: Cases were posted one day before class, to achieve more reasoning skills and to become effective.

Step 2: Arrangement of the classroom by creating a “circle of chairs” and forming inner and outer circles by students.

Step 3: Explain the protocol. The inner circle of students is the one who will initiate the discussion among themselves for a given case. The time allotted for each case was 10 minutes. The outer circle

of students should be focused, observed, and should make notes regarding the discussion. Not allowed to speak. After ten minutes the facilitator will say “Switch”. At that time outer circle of students will sit on chairs and become the inner circle and they will become speakers.

Step 4: At the end, a facilitator will wrap up the discussion.

Jigsaw Methodology

Figure 2:

Step 1: Creating a “home group”. 48 students were divided into subgroups of 12 and each subgroup had 4 students.

Step 2: Cases were allotted to each student present in the subgroup.

Step 3: Creating an “Expert group”. That is selecting one student from each subgroup who has similar cases. Created 4 expert groups.

Step 4: For all expert groups, the time was allotted for 15-20 minutes for discussion.

Step 5: The expert group will return to their respective “home groups” and they will present the case.

Step 6: At the end, the facilitator will wind up the discussion of each case

Flipped Classroom Methodology

Figure 3: Bloom's Taxonomy

Step 1: Pre-reading resources were given one day before class.

Step 2: In the classroom, students were allowed to read themselves either individually or groups. The allotted time was 45 minutes.

Step 3: At the end, the facilitator will discuss the cases.

Assessment was done for all three 3 rounds by conducting pre-test and post-test which were based on MCQs. Feedback was taken from both students and facilitators.

Results were analyzed by using MS Excel and SPSS software versions. Evaluation of the teaching tool was done by using the Kirkpatrick model (levels 1 and 2 were assessed).

Level 1: student’s perception towards FCR, FB & JG was assessed by feedback’s questionnaires.

Level 2: Student’s learning is assessed by Pre test & Post test by MCQ’s

Results: All characteristics were summarized descriptively. For continuous variables, the summary statistics of mean ± standard deviation (SD) were used. The difference in the means of analysis variables between two-time points in the

same group was tested by paired t-test. The difference in the means of answers in variables between more than two independent groups was tested by ANOVA and F test of testing of equality of Variance. If the p-value was < 0.05, then the results were statistically significant. Data were analysed evusing SPSS software v.23 (IBM Statistics, Chicago, USA) and Microsoft Office 2007.

Table 1: Round one showing pre-test & post-test (Mean ± SD) & (Mean Difference) of all 3 techniques

Groups	Pretest		Post-test		Mean Difference	p-value	95% CI	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			Lower	Upper
Jigsaw method	3.8	2.0	6.3	2.1	2.5	<0.001*	-3.1	-1.9
Flipped classroom	3.9	1.6	7.0	1.7	3.2	<0.001*	-3.8	-2.6
Fish Bowl	3.8	1.9	6.6	2.0	2.8	<0.001*	-3.4	-2.1

Figure 4: Shows a graphical representation of the pre-test and post-test (Mean and mean difference) of round 1 on all three methods

Table 2: Round two shows the pre-test and post-test (Mean±SD) and (Mean Difference) of all 3 techniques

Groups	Pretest		Post-test		Mean Difference	p-value	95% CI	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			Lower	Upper
Jigsaw method	5.2	1.6	7.4	1.6	2.2	<0.001*	-2.8	-1.7
Flipped classroom	4.9	1.6	7.8	1.2	2.9	<0.001*	-3.4	-2.5
Fish Bowl	5.0	1.9	7.5	1.7	2.5	<0.001*	-3.2	-1.9

Figure 5: Shows a graphical representation of the pre-test and post-test (Mean and mean difference) of round 2 on all three methods

Table 3: Round three shows the pre-test and post-test (Mean±SD) and (Mean Difference) of all 3 techniques

Groups	Pretest		Post test		Mean Difference	p value	95% CI	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			Lower	Upper
Jigsaw method	4.3	1.8	6.1	2.0	1.8	<0.001*	-2.5	-1.1
Flipped classroom	3.9	1.7	6.2	1.9	2.2	<0.001*	-2.9	-1.6
Fish Bowl	4.6	1.9	6.2	1.6	1.7	<0.001*	-2.4	-0.9

Figure 6: Shows a graphical representation of the pre-test & and post-test (Mean and mean difference) of round 3 on all three methods

Table 4: Shows feedback questionnaire which is based on the likert scale

1. Pre reading materials were available before class?
2. Adequate time was given before class?
3. Pre reading and ppt were relevant for classroom discussion?
4. Classroom arrangement was conducive?
5. Activities during class session improved my understanding of the key concepts.
6. Activities inspired to perceive further learning?
7. More lectures should be conducted by today's method?
8. Instructor was able to engage me in the activity?
9. Instructor was able to provide clarification on difficult concepts during activity?
10. Whether instructor was able to expand on pre-reading materials during classroom?

Figure 7: FISH BOWL Technique (N=137)

Figure 8: JIGSAW Technique (N=135)

Figure 9: Flipped classroom technique (N=136)

Table 5: Feedback questionnaire from Facilitators which rated from 1 to 5

Feedback Form
Was this FB/JS/FCR relevant clinically to discuss the cases?
Did this FB/JS/FCR provide a non-threatening low stake learning group environment to the students?
Was this FB/JS/FCR suitable to implement integration of learning with higher phases subject?
Was this FB/JS/FCR suitable to give pedagogical material that encourages problem solving?
Was this type of FB/JS/FCR help students to ask to questions & interact?
Is this FB/JS/FCR technique feasible to conduct?
Was this FB/JS/FCR technique suitable for the topic discussed?

Figure 8: Shows a graphical representation of the average rating for each question from Facilitators

Discussion

Generally, in Case based learning, the instructor/teacher will present the case & doesn't interact intensively with students, again where it's becoming teacher-centered learning i.e. passive teaching method. As we are aware of knowledge retention rates of the learning pyramid which have shown that by doing "lecturing", the knowledge retention rate is 5%, but if there is an activity among students such as "discussion" among groups or "teaching others" have shown that knowledge retention rate has tremendously increased to 50% and 90% respectively. That is the main motto of this study.

Thus, in our study we made an activity among students by applying fishbowl, jigsaw and flipped classroom method for case scenarios and conducted thrice with different case scenario topics, so that each student should be exposed to each technique.

There is a colossal improvement in all three techniques where we conducted pre-test & post-test for an analysis (Table No.1, 2 & 3 shows Mean $\pm$ SD). Among all three techniques, Flipped Classroom showed higher Mean $\pm$ SD successively in 1st, 2nd & 3rd rounds which was highly statistically significant $p < 0.001$) compared to Fishbowl and Jigsaw. In third round, along with FCR, the Fishbowl method showed higher mean values.

On other hand, a study conducted by Hanadi et al., showed positive perception towards FCR which was a case control study & compared to traditional lecture method [13]. FCR, was a proven technique in a systematic review which consisted of 82 papers showed student's impetus & diligent [14]. Another study conducted via meta-analysis of forty-six pa-

pers included 9,000 participants showed higher academic execution [15]. Fishbowl, an interactive activity which improves listening & immersed among students [7]. Amitha et al., study combined with snowball along with FB technique showed increased comprehension & retention of concepts [16].

Even the feedback's from the students for all 3 teaching techniques showed positive encouragement & have emanated interest in biochemistry & not only that they also want to cover more topics by any one of above activities. Feedback's from all facilitators feels the same & showed positive response to all 3 activities. Thus, by introducing any above method would lead to small group discussions where students will become more alert, focused & provides an opportunity for one-to-one interaction within group. Thereby peer pressure indirectly beneficial to the students.

Conclusion

By applying interactive session for case-based learning especially flipped classroom & fishbowl method showed positive fortify & better performance among first year medical students.

Limitations

1. It was non-randomized study.
2. Evaluation assessed by Kirkpatrick model; level 3 (measures behavior changes after learning) & level 4 (focuses on whether the targeted outcomes resulted or not from training program) couldn't assess.
3. Since topics were varied, it may lead to biased.

References

1. Amandeep K, Sahiba K, Tejinder S, et al. Early clinical exposure to enhance the learning of biochemistry in first-year M.B.B.S students. *International Journal of Clinical Biochemistry and Research*. 2018; 5(3):401-5.
2. Nair SP, Shah T, Seth S, et al. Case-based learning: a method for better understanding of biochemistry in medical students. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*. 2013; 7(8): 1576-8.
3. Fernandez-Santander. Cooperative learning combined with short periods of lecturing: A good alternative in teaching biochemistry. *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Education*. 2008;36 (1):34-38.
4. Lestari, W., Selvia, F., & Layliyyah, R. Open-ended approach to students' metacognitive ability. *At-Ta'lim: Journal of Education*, 2019; 5(2):93-106.
5. <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/7159708>.
6. Andréia Machado Cardoso, Flávia Medeiros Dutra Reis, Lorryayne Camila Moreira, Maurício Lanzini, Mayara Luiza da Silva Lopes. Use of case reports and fishbowl to complement the teaching of biochemistry for medical courses *Rev Med (São Paulo)*. 2021 Nov-Dec;100(6):554-60
7. Gandham Pavani. Fishbowl Teaching Technique for IInd MBBS students in AIMS. *J.Evolution Med. Dent. Sci*. 2016; 5(32):1713-1715.
8. Neetha Kundoor, Sukumar Sannidhi, Srilatha Bashetty. Effectiveness of fishbowl method in teaching clinical biochemistry for Ist year medical students. *Int.j.med.sci.educ*. 2019; 6(1):27-31.
9. Suma Dnyanesh, Sheetal Vishwanath Patanshetti, Shilpa M Bhimalli, Daksha Dixit. Jigsaw Technique: An Innovative teaching strategy in Anatomy *J Sci Soc*. 2022; 49:322-5.
10. Cochon Drouet O, Lentillon-Kaestner V and Margas N. Effects of the Jigsaw method on student educational outcomes: systematic review and meta-analyses. 2023 *Front. Psychol*. 14:121643
11. O. Sagsoz, O. Karatas, V. Turel, M. Yildiz1 and E. Kaya. Effectiveness of Jigsaw learning compared to lecture-based learning in dental education *Eur J Dent Educ*. 2017; 21: 28–32.
12. Arathi. M. S, G. Durga Devi, Krishnaveni Sharith, WMS. Johnson, Ashini Bhandari. Effectiveness of Flipped Classroom Approach as a Teaching Methodology in Anatomy for Early Clinical Exposure Modules for First-Year Medical Students – An Interventional Study. *Int J Anat Res* 2022; 10(1):8255-8261.
13. Hanadi Abdelgadir Ahmed Sourg, Shahenaz Satti, Nasereldin Ahmed and Adil Ballal Mohammed Ahmed. Impact of flipped classroom model in increasing the achievement for medical students *BMC Medical Education*. 2023; 23:287; 1-9.
14. Chen F, Lui AM, Martinelli SM. A systematic review of the effectiveness of flipped classrooms in medical education. *Med Educ*. 2017; 51: 585 – 97.
15. Chen KS, Monrouxe L, Lu YH et al. Academic outcomes of flipped classroom learning: a meta-analysis. *Med Educ*. 2018; 52: 910 – 24.
16. Amitha M. Hegde1 Shreema Shetty2 Deepshikha Mehrotra1 Comparison of Classroom Lectures with Fishbowl Snowball Activity for Dental Undergraduate Students: An Observational Study. *Journal of Health and Allied Sciences*. 2023; 13:395-399.